

PERCEPTION OF WORKERS IN KERALA DINESH BEEDI WORKERS CENTRAL COOPERATIVE SOCIETY LIMITED

Key words: *Compensation, Employment status, Motivation, Working conditions*

Abstract

Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society, one of the largest Industrial societies in India started its operation during the year 1969 at Kannur district. At the initial stage the society dealt with only beedi products. When the government banned smoking at the public places, the demand for beedi products reduced and has recorded a steep fall in sales and the production also got affected due to poor off take by the agents from within the state and outside which in turn affected the existence of the society and its workers. For the workers of KDB it was their main income and it became difficult for them to survive. So the society thought about product diversification. The first unit under product diversification of the central society was coconut milk extraction in 1997, curry powder pickle unit in 1998, fruit processing unit and Dinesh software in 1999, umbrella assembling unit in 2000 and finally Dinesh garments in 2007 with advanced technology to produce export quality products. One speciality of the central society was that all the workers of diversified units were beedi workers and their relatives. That means the workers are of two category; those who joined the society before diversification (Beedi workers) and who joined after diversification. This article attempts to analyse the workers perception about the diversified units and to evaluate whether there is any difference in the perception of employees of both category.

Introduction

The Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society (KDBWCCS), one of the largest industrial co-operative societies in India which started operating at Kannur District in 1969. At the initial stage society was dealing with only Beedi products. It provided full employment opportunities to 12000 people directly and more than 100000 people indirectly through all their functional units. Later when there was a strong decline in the Beedi market it affected the sale of beedi. The central society was not able to pay proper wages to its employees in time. Consequently it led to think of diversification. The society's first diversified product was "Kera milk" started in

the year 1997. Later it started various other divisions such as Dinesh Foods, Dinesh Umbrella, Dinesh Garments, Dinesh software and Dinesh Auditorium.

Employees in all these units consist of beedi workers, their relatives and other newly recruited employees. Employees of Dinesh Foods and Dinesh Umbrella include both the beedi workers and other recruited category. The study aims to compare the level of satisfaction of employees of both these categories. Dinesh garments, the latest diversified unit of the society started in the year 2007 does not include beedi workers. Employees of Dinesh garments include only the relatives of beedi workers and other recruited employees.

Research Problem

The Central Cooperative Society gave more importance to their employees and it was one among the reason for diversifying their units. One of the specialities of the society was that majority of the employees of the diversified units were beedi workers and their relatives So there is a need to analyse the manner in which workers perceive the diversified units and also to know whether there is any difference in the perception among employees who joined the society before diversification and after diversification.

Significance of the Study

The present study deals with diversification programme undertaken by Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society (KDBWCCS). Government had granted Rs. 4 crore to the Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society for the purpose of diversification programme undertaken by them. Using these funds the society gave birth to different products. The workers who handled tobacco for 25 years are now handling spices, juice, jam, umbrella etc. The society gave more emphasis on their workers. The study has been undertaken to know the workers perception towards all diversified units.

Scope of the Study

The study deals with diversification programme undertaken by Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society (KDBWCCS). The scope of the study is limited to only three units of the society. They are Dinesh Garments, Dinesh Foods and Dinesh Umbrella, as they are the

leading diversified units of the Central Co-operative Society. The study mainly focuses on employees of the three units.

Review of Literature

Literature reviews are conducted to know in detail about the particular areas of the study and to identify research gap. Many studies have been conducted about Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Cooperative Society. Studies were conducted by both national and international researchers. Details of available literatures are depicted here.

Rashmid P.V (2009) conducted a study entitled 'Employees Absenteeism of Kerala Dinesh Food Products'. From the study it was found that even though there exists a good relation between employees and employers in the organization, the rate of absenteeism was more. And also the employees are not satisfied with the leave schedule and salary provided to them.

Mittu Gulati G, Thomas. M. Issac and William. A. Klein (2002) presented a paper entitled 'When a Worker's Cooperative works: The case of Kerala Dinesh Beedi'. This paper presents a case study of a large worker cooperative in South India that has worked well for a long time. This cooperative illustrates, among other things, that worker control and worker democracy are not necessarily inconsistent with the degree of hierarchy and delegation that may be essential to effective operation. The cooperative has been able to compete despite paying wages and benefits that are dramatically higher than those paid by its competitors, while at the same time providing far better working condition. Part of the explanation is good fortune at its inception in attracting effective, honest and dedicated managers and, subsequently, in avoiding government involvement and in being able to ignore cumbersome and unsuitable legal rules.

Raveendran P.V (1990) in his study entitled 'A Study on the Art of the Financial Management in Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Cooperative Society Ltd. Kannur was conducted to know about the capital structure of the organisation, their overall income and return on investment over the period of the study and also about the working capital. It was concluded that liquidity position of the society was satisfactory. The main aim of the society was not making profit. It was aimed to rehabilitate the unemployed beedi workers of Kannur District.

Mohan P (1987) in his study entitled 'Prospects and Problems of Beedi Marketing: A Case study of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Cooperative Central Society Cannanore.' was

conducted to analyse the cost structure, operational aspects, and analysis of production and marketing trends and about labour benefits. It was concluded that KDBC has a good scope for expanding production, marketing and employment. Primarily recruit workers, train and enrol them as members. It has a very good system of employee's remuneration. Besides a high basic rate, the workers enjoy a host of other cash and non cash benefits such as leave wages, maternity benefits and pension. Trade unions had played a vital role in the KDBC's management. Still the society has been facing several problems like cost over runs, threat from spurious beedis, burden of excise duty and recovery variation.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the satisfaction level of workers of different units.
2. To evaluate the satisfaction level of workers of pre-post modernisation period.

Hypotheses

Based on the above mentioned objectives the following hypothesis has been framed.

1. There is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of workers of all units with regard to wages.
2. There is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of worker in the pre- post modernisation period with regard to the wages and working conditions.

Research Methodology and Data Base

The present study has been designed as a descriptive one based on both primary data and secondary data.

Secondary Data

The secondary data, necessary for the study has been collected from various sources:

- Byelaw of the central cooperative society
- Annual reports published by the society.
- Journals
- Magazines
- Websites of KDB

Primary Data

Since most of the information necessary to fulfil the objectives of the study is not available from secondary data, the study is mainly based on primary data collected through a sample survey of workers of KDBWCCS using structured and pre-tested questionnaire. Discussions were conducted with officials and experts at the top level.

Sample Design

Only three units of the society were taken for the study; Dinesh foods, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments. Samples were drawn from employees of these three units. 80 samples were drawn from the employees of all the three diversified units of the society. Among them 30 samples were drawn from the employees of Dinesh Garments using simple random sampling method. 26 samples were drawn from Dinesh Umbrella using stratified random sampling method. Here the employees are classified into two strata on the basis of pre post employment status. And finally 24 samples were drawn from Dinesh Foods also using stratified random sampling method, which includes 12 employees from those who joined the society before modernisation and 12 from after modernisation.

Tools used for Data Collection

Field survey was conducted to collect primary data from the employees of KDBWCCS. A well structured interview schedule was developed for collecting data from employees of KDB. For the purpose of the study a pilot survey was conducted among the employees and customers of diversified units of the society. On the basis of the experience of the pilot survey, the questions were revised and schedule was redrafted. Interview schedule developed for the purpose of the study was the tools for data collection.

Tools for Data Analysis

For the purpose of data analysis various statistical tools and mathematical techniques were used such as:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi square test
- Mann Whitney U test

- Kruskal Wallis test
- Weighted average method

List of Variables used for the Study

To study the perception of workers towards the society, the following variables were used.

- Training
- Wages/Salary
- Overtime work
- Motivational measures
- Working conditions

Limitations of the Study

As in the case of almost all social science research, this study is also not free from certain inherent limitations as stated below:

1. Most of the primary data collected from respondents are based on their memories, and may be subject to memory errors.
2. Top level executives were reluctant to reveal all necessary information, in spite of assurance that the data would be used only for research purpose.
3. Being a social study, the study is not free from the defects of social investigation.

Results and Discussion

Employment Status during the Pre-post Modernisation Periods

Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society includes the employees who joined the society at the earlier stage with beedi and also who joined the society after diversification. So the employees of these three units are classified into two groups viz employees recruited before modernisation and after modernisation. In case of Dinesh foods 12 employees were joined the society before modernisation, so in that proportion 12 more employees were selected from the unit who joined the society after modernisation. In case of Dinesh umbrella only 13 employees, joined the society after modernisation and all other employees were beedi workers. So among them 13 employees were also selected. But one speciality of Dinesh garments is that it includes only those employees who joined the society after modernisation. The following table

clearly specifies the pre-post employment status of all the three units of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society.

Table 1.1: Pre post modernisation - employment status

Year	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Before Modernisation	12	50	13	50	0	0.00	25	31.25
After Modernisation	12	50	13	50	30	100	55	68.75
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

The above table clearly reveals that employees of two units; Dinesh Foods and Dinesh Umbrella include the employees who joined the society before modernisation and after modernisation. But Dinesh Garments does not include beedi employees. All the employees of these units are those who joined the society after modernisation. Equal numbers of employees are taken from both category of Dinesh food and Dinesh umbrella.

Training Facilities

Employees of all three units of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society were beedi workers or their relatives. They were not familiar with this field. So in order to know whether the society has taken any measures to provide training to their employees various data are collected. The following table clearly specifies the employees opinion that whether the society had provided training to them.

Table 1.2: Distribution of training availed from the society

Training availed	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	15	62.50	24	92.31	21	70.00	60	75.00
No	9	37.50	2	7.69	9	30.00	20	25.00
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

Majority of employees (62.5 per cent) of Dinesh foods, 92.31 per cent employees of Dinesh umbrella and 70 per cent of employees of Dinesh Garments responded that the society have taken necessary measures to provide training to the employees. However 37.50 per cent of the employees engaged in the food division did not undergo any training.

Effectiveness of Training

As per the above table, it is clear that overall 75 per cent employees of all the three units were of the opinion that the society had provided training to make them familiar with their units. So it is necessary to know how the employees rate the utility of training or the effectiveness of training. In order to know the employees opinion about the effectiveness of training they have undergone, their opinions were seeked and the result of the same is presented in table below.

Table 1.3: Distribution of effectiveness of training undergone

Rate of training	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Very useful	10	66.67	20	83.33	13	61.90	43	71.67
Useful	5	33.33	4	16.67	6	28.57	15	25.00
Some what useful	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	9.53	2	3.33
Total	15	100.00	24	100.00	21	100.00	60	100.00

Pearson Chi-square: 5.69, df=4, p value=.2233

Source: Primary data

Majority of employees of Dinesh foods (66.67 per cent), Dinesh umbrella (83.33 per cent) and Dinesh Garments (61.9 per cent) has the opinion that training programme conducted by the central society was very useful. One note able point is that only 9.53 per cent employees of Dinesh garments were of the opinion that the training provided was somewhat useful.

As the p value (.2233) is greater than .05 it can be said that there is no significant difference between the opinions of employees of all the three units of the society (Dinesh foods, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments) with regard to the effectiveness of training provided to them. That means the opinion of the employees of all the three units about the effectiveness of training is same.

Necessity of Training

As per the table 1.2, 3/4th of the employees opined that they availed the training facilities and the remaining 1/4th did not availed training. In order to know about the opinion of employees that whether there is any need for training to make them familiar with their respective units, the results of various information collected is presented in the table below.

Table 1.4: Distribution of necessity of training

Training necessary	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	23	95.83	26	100.00	25	83.33	74	92.50
No	1	4.17	0	0.00	5	16.67	6	7.50
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

As per the above table, 95.83 per cent employees of Dinesh foods, 100 per cent of the employees of Dinesh umbrella and 83.33 per cent employees of Dinesh Garments opined that there is a need for training. So it can be concluded that majority of the employees of all units were of the opinion that training is indispensable.

Compensation Management

The central co-operative society provides compensation to their employees in the form of wages for the work done by them. It is necessary to know whether the employees are satisfied with the wages paid to them by the society. As the employees in the diversified units of the society includes those who joined the society before modernisation and who joined after modernisation, it is necessary to know whether there is any difference in the satisfaction level of employees of both the category with regard to their wages. Only in case of Dinesh foods and Dinesh umbrella these two categories of employees are there. So the level of satisfaction of employees of these two units is analysed separately using Mann Whitney U test. But in case of Dinesh garments, it includes only those employees who joined the society after modernisation. The following table represents the satisfaction level of employees of all the three units with regard to the wages paid to them by the society.

**Table 1.5: Distribution of satisfaction level of employees
with regard to wages**

Satisfied with wages	Umbrella		Garment		Food		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Highly Satisfied	0	0.00	2	6.67	1	4.17	3	3.75
Satisfied	4	15.38	9	30.00	9	37.50	22	27.50
Not so satisfied	12	46.16	12	40.00	7	29.17	31	38.75
Not at all satisfied	10	38.46	7	23.33	7	29.16	24	30.00
Total	26	100.00	30	100.00	24	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

Majority of the employees of all the three units are not so satisfied with the wages paid to them by the society. If three units are treated separately then the employees of Dinesh foods are satisfied with the wages paid to them. But in case of Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments they are not so satisfied with the wages. Altogether only very few employees are highly satisfied with the wages paid.

In order to compare the satisfaction level of employees of all the three units viz. Dinesh foods, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments Kruskal-Wallis test is used. Employees opinion about their wages are analysed and the result of each division is presented in the table below.

**Table 1.6: Satisfaction of employees about compensation
using Kruskal Wallis test**

Products	Median	N	Avg. Rank	d.f	P-Value
Food	3.00	24	37.46		
Umbrella	3.00	26	47.50		
Garments	3.00	30	36.87		
Total	3.00	80		2	.1409

Source: Primary data

As per the above table, Median of all the three units is 3.00. The average rank of Dinesh food is 37.46, Dinesh umbrella is 47.50 and that of Dinesh garments is 36.87. P value at degrees of freedom 2 using Kruskal-Wallis test is .1409.

In order to test whether there is any difference in the satisfaction level of employees in all the three units of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society the following hypothesis was formulated.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of workers of all units with regard to wages.

Since the p-value (0.1409) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis formulated would be accepted. So it can be concluded that the satisfaction level of workers of Dinesh food; Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments are same.

Dinesh Food

Since the employees working in this unit include the employees of both categories i.e. who joined the society before modernisation and after modernisation, it is necessary to know whether there is any difference in the satisfaction level of employees of both categories with regard to wages. Employee's opinions about their wages are analysed using Mann Whitney U test and the result is shown in the table below.

Table 1.7: Result of wage- based satisfaction level of employees of Dinesh foods using Mann Whitney U test

Category	N	Sum of Ranks	P Value
Before modernisation	12	209	
After modernisation	12	91	
Total	24	300	.0004

Source: Primary data

As per the above table, employees are categorised into two, before modernisation and after modernisation. Samples drawn from both the category are equal i.e., 12. Sum of ranks of employees before modernisation is 209 and after modernisation are 91 to a total of 300. P value of employee's satisfaction of both the category of Dinesh food using Mann Whitney U test is .0004.

Dinesh Umbrella

Employees working in this unit also include the employees of both categories i.e. before modernisation and after modernisation. So it is necessary to know whether there is any change in the satisfaction level of employees of both categories with regard to wages. The result of employees opinion analysed using Mann Whitney U test are shown below.

Table 1.8: Result of wage based satisfaction level of employees of Dinesh umbrella using Mann Whitney U test

Category	N	Sum of ranks	P value
Before modernisation	13	192.5	
After modernisation	13	158.5	
Total	26	351	.3566

Source: Primary data

As per the above table, employees of Dinesh umbrella are also classified into two categories i.e. before modernisation and after modernisation. Sample size (N) of each unit is 13. Sum of ranks of employees before modernisation is 192.5 and after modernisation is 158.5 to a total of 351. P value of employee's opinion about the wages of Dinesh umbrella using Mann Whitney U test is .3566.

In order to test whether there is any significant difference in the satisfaction level of employees of both the categories with regard to wages paid to them, the following hypothesis is formulated.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of worker in the pre- post modernisation period with regard to wages.

Since the p value of the Dinesh Foods (.0004) is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected. So it can be concluded that satisfaction level of worker in the pre- post modernisation period with regard to wages is different. But in case of Dinesh Umbrella p value obtained is (.3566) is greater than .05, so null hypothesis formulated can be accepted. So it can be concluded that in case of umbrella unit there is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of worker in the pre- post modernisation period with regard to wages.

Overtime Work

It is a usual practice of providing overtime to the workers to meet the excess/ seasonal demand on the product. Only during that particular season when the demand for the product is high, there would be overtime work. The society's position in this regard is presented in the following table.

Table 1.9: Distribution of overtime work

Overtime work	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	23	95.83	25	96.15	14	46.67	62	77.50
No	1	4.17	1	3.85	16	53.33	18	22.50
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

The overtime work arises only during some season when demand for their product increases. In case of fruit processing unit the demand for their products increases during summer season, demand for umbrella rises during rainy seasons and demand for other food items such as Kera milk and garment products increases during festival seasons such as Onam, Christmas, marriage etc. The above table clearly reveals about the employees opinion about the overtime works availed by them. Majority of the employees of Dinesh foods (95.83 per cent) and Dinesh umbrella (96.15 per cent) were of the opinion that there was overtime work in their unit. But about 53.33 per cent employees of Dinesh garments responded that there was no overtime work. Overall 77.5 per cent employees opined that there was overtime work.

Employee's Satisfaction with Regard to Overtime Wages

As per the table 1.9, overall 77.50 per cent employees of the central society were of the opinion that there was overtime work during the season of heavy demand for the product. So in order to know whether these employees are satisfied with their overtime pay necessary information has been collected. Employees opinion about the overtime wages paid to them are shown in the tabular form below:

Table 1.10: Satisfaction with Regard to Overtime Wages

Satisfied with overtime	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	11	47.83	9	36.00	8	57.14	28	45.16
No	12	52.17	16	64.00	6	42.86	34	54.84
Total	23	100.00	25	100.00	14	100.00	62	100.00

Source: Primary data

Above table reveals the employees opinion whether they are satisfied with the overtime wages provided to them. Most of the employees of Dinesh foods (52.17 per cent) and Dinesh umbrella (64 per cent) are not satisfied with the overtime wages provided to them. But 55.14 per cent employees of Dinesh garments are satisfied with the overtime wages paid to them. Overall 54.84 per cent employees of the society are not satisfied with the overtime wages paid to them.

Income of the Family other than Wages from the Society

In order to know whether there is any other income in the family of employees necessary information's are collected from them. And if this income is the one and only one income to their family, it is necessary to know whether they are able to meet their household expenses or not. The following table clearly specifies that whether there is any other income to the families of the employees other than this wages.

Table 1.11: Distribution of income of the family other than wages from the society

Other income	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	3	12.50	17	65.38	20	66.67	40	50.00
No	21	87.50	9	34.62	10	33.33	40	50.00
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

Most of the employees of Dinesh food (87.5 per cent) were of the opinion that there was no other income to their family other than the wages paid to them by the society. But majority of the

employees of Dinesh umbrella (65.38 per cent) and Dinesh garments (66.67 per cent) opined that there is other income to their family other than this wages.

Incentives

Large numbers of employees are working under each units of the central society. So in order to know whether the society had undertaken any steps to motivate the employees to work well, necessary information's have been collected. Following table clearly specifies the employee's opinion about incentives provided by the society.

Table 1.12: Distribution of Incentives to Employees

Incentive	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	15	62.50	24	92.31	28	93.33	67	83.75
No	9	37.50	2	7.69	2	6.67	13	16.25
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

From the above table, it is clear that overall 83.75 per cent employees of the society were of the opinion that the central society provides incentives to motivate the employees to work well and only 16.25 per cent employees opined that the society have not taken any measures to work well. About 62.50 per cent employees of Dinesh Food, 92.31 per cent employees of Dinesh umbrella and 93.33 per cent employees of Dinesh Garments respond that society provides incentives to motivate them to work well. One notable point is that only less than 10 per cent employees of Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments suggested that the society has not provided any incentives.

Working Conditions of Employees

Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society gives more focus on their employees. Employees are influenced by many factors. Working condition is one of the most important factors which influence them. Only if there is a better working conditions, employees will be motivated to work well. Otherwise they may not be interested to do their work in prompt manner. The central society has taken necessary measures to provide better working conditions to their employees. Employees of the central society are classified into two categories, before modernisation and after modernisation. Dinesh foods and Dinesh umbrella includes the employees

of both category and Dinesh garments includes only those employees who joined the society after the modernisation.

In order to know the overall satisfaction of employees with the working conditions provided to them by the society necessary information has been collected. And it is clearly depicted in the table shown below:

Table 1.13: Distribution of Satisfaction Level of Employees based on Working Conditions

Satisfied working conditions	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Highly Satisfied	3	12.50	0	0.00	1	3.33	4	5.00
Satisfied	9	37.50	18	69.23	24	80.00	51	63.75
Not so satisfied	5	20.83	8	30.77	4	13.34	17	21.25
Not at all satisfied	7	29.17	0	0.00	1	3.33	8	10.00
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Pearson Chi-square: 22.87, df=6, p=.0008

Source: Primary data

Majority of the employees of Dinesh food (37.50 per cent), Dinesh umbrella (69.23 per cent) and Dinesh garments (80 per cent) are satisfied with the working conditions provided by the society. Overall only 5 per cent of the employees of all the units are highly satisfied. And 21.25 per cent employees of all the three units are not so satisfied with the working condition provided by the society.

Since the p value (.0008) at the degrees of freedom 6 is less than .05, it can be concluded that satisfaction level of workers of all the three units Dinesh food, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments on the basis of working conditions provided by the central society is different.

Dinesh Food

Dinesh food is the first diversified unit of the central society. It includes the employees of both categories who joined the society before modernisation and after modernisation. The central society undertakes necessary measures to provide better working conditions to their employees. So it is necessary to know whether there is any difference in the satisfaction level of workers of both

the category with respect to working conditions provided by the society. For this purpose a sample of 24 was selected which includes 12 each from both the category. Datas collected were analysed using Mann Whitney U test and the result of the analysis are shown in the table below

Table 1.14: Result of satisfaction level of employees of both category of Dinesh Food using Wilcoxon - Mann/Whitney Test

Category	N	Sum of Ranks	P-value
Before Modernisation	12	184	
After Modernisation	12	116	
Total	24	300	.0444

Source: Primary data

As per the table 4.19, it is clear that the sample size is 24 which include 12 from each category. Sum of ranks of the employees before modernisation is 184 and that of after modernisation is 116 to a total of 300. So in order to test whether there is any difference in the satisfaction level of employees of both of the categories, the following hypothesis was formulated.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of worker in the pre- post modernisation period with regard to their working conditions.

Since the p- value (.0444) is less than .05, the null hypothesis will be rejected. So it can be concluded that there is significant difference in the satisfaction level of employees of both period of Dinesh Foods with regard to the working conditions provided by the central society.

Dinesh Umbrella

Dinesh umbrella unit also include the employees of both categories. In order to test whether there is any difference in the satisfaction level of workers who joined the society before modernisation and after modernisation with regard to the working conditions provided by the society various information was collected and was analysed using Mann Whitney Test. Result obtained from the analysis is summarised in the following table below:

Table 1.15: Result of employee's satisfaction with regard to the working condition provided using Wilcoxon - Mann/Whitney Test

Category	N	Sum of Ranks	P-value
Before Modernisation	13	156	
After Modernisation	13	195	
Total	26	351	.2374

Source: Primary data

Sample size as per the above table to evaluate the satisfaction level of employees of both categories of Dinesh umbrella is 26 which includes 13 each from both category. Sum of ranks of employees who joined the society before modernisation is 156 and after modernisation are 195.

Since the p-value (.2374) is greater than .05, the null hypothesis can be accepted. So it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of employees of both periods of Dinesh umbrella with regard to the working conditions provided to them by the society.

Patronage towards Dinesh Products

The society gave more focus on their employees. It provided the products at low price than the market price to their employees. So it is necessary to know whether the employees have taken any steps to patronage the products of KDB. For that purpose various information was collected from the employees and it is represented in the tabular form below.

Table 1.16: Patronage towards Dinesh Products

Patronage Dinesh Products	Food		Umbrella		Garment		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	24	100.00	26	100.00	22	73.33	72	90
No	0	0.00	0	0.00	8	26.67	8	10
Total	24	100.00	26	100.00	30	100.00	80	100.00

Source: Primary data

100 per cent employees of both units Dinesh Umbrella and Dinesh food, patronage the products of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society. Only 26.67 per cent employees of Dinesh garments do not patronage the products of the central society. Overall 90 per cent employees of all the three units patronage the products of the central society.

Employee's Patronage towards Dinesh Products

There are different ways for the employees to patronage the products of the society, such as buying the products, recommending the products to friends and relatives and so on. So it is necessary to know in which manner the employee's patronage Dinesh products. The important factors of Dinesh products that influenced the workers are its quality, price, after sales service and credit availability. Following table reveals the manner in which the employees patronage the products.

Table 1.17: Distribution of weighted average of Employee's patronage towards Dinesh Products

Influencing Factors	Food	Umbrella	Garments	Total Weight	Weighted Average	Rank
Buying the product	136	140	109	385	18.33	1
Recommending to friends and relatives	110	116	105	331	15.76	3
High quality	114	115	106	335	15.95	2
Reasonable Price	69	97	76	242	11.52	4
After sales service	45	45	37	127	6.05	5
Credit availability	30	33	29	92	4.39	6

Source: Primary data

In order to identify the employee's patronage towards Dinesh products, they are asked to rank according to their preference. Weights are assigned to each factor on the basis of the ranks given. Highest rank is given the weight six, then five given to next highest rank and so on. In this manner weights are assigned to each factor of all units. Sum total of the weight of each factors of all units are shown in the column, total weight. Weighted average is obtained by dividing total weight by 21 (6+5+4+3+2+1). The ranks are given on the basis of weighted average; the factor having highest weighted average is given the first rank and so on.

As per the above table first rank is given to the factor buying the product, which means most of the employee's patronage Dinesh products by buying them. The second important factor that influenced the workers was its high quality. And thirdly they patronage Dinesh products by recommending to their friends and relatives.

Non Patronage of Dinesh Products

As per table 1.16, only 10 per cent of the total employees of all the three units do not patronage the products of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society. One notable point is that only 26.67 per cent employees of Dinesh garments are not patronising the products of the society. All other employee's patronage Dinesh products. So it is necessary to know the reason for the not patronising the products

Table 1.18: Distribution of non patronage of Dinesh products

If NO	Umbrella		Garment		Food		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Percent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Do not use the product	0	0.00	7	87.50	0	0.00	7	87.50
Bad after sales service	0	0.00	1	12.50	0	0.00	1	12.50
Total	0	0.00	8	100.00	0	0.00	8	100.00

Source: Primary data

From the above table it is clear that only the employee's of Dinesh Garments are not patronising their products much. As per table 1.16, it is clear that 26.67 per cent employees of Dinesh Garments are not patronising Dinesh products. Among them 87.50 per cent of employees do not patronage the product because they do not use the product and 12.50 per cent employees were of the opinion that their after sales service was bad.

Conclusions

The present paper is focused on the three units of the society viz foods, umbrella and garments. An attempt is made to analysis the perception of workers towards the diversified units.. In order to identify workers perception about Dinesh products sufficient information were collected from the workers and were analysed using statistical tools and was found that workers are satisfied with the working conditions provided to them but not satisfied with the wages paid to them. If both the categories are treated separately it was found that their opinion differ in case of food unit but is same in case of umbrella unit. If the society takes necessary steps to solve these problems will lead to success of all units because employees are the main factors.

Bibliography

A. Books

Bhattacharya, Dipak Kumar, *Research Methodology*, Excel Books, New Delhi, 2006.

Dessler, Gary, *Human Resource Management*, Pearson College Division, 2010.

Jackson, Sherri L, *Research Methods and Statistics*, Wadsworth/ Thomson Learning, USA, 2003.

Jain, Gopal Lal, *Research Methodology Tools and Techniques*, Mangal Deep Publications, 2003.

Kothari, C.R., *Research Methodology Methods and Techniques*, New Age International Publishing House, New Delhi, 2009.

Krishnaswamy, O.R. and Obul Reddy D, *Research Methodology and Statistical Tools*, Himalaya Publications, Mumbai, 2009.

Kumar, Ranjit, *Research Methodology*, Sage Publications, 2010.

Mondy, Wayne and Judy Bandy, *Human Resource Management*, Prentice Hall, 2010.

Panicker, G.K , '*Thrilling story of Dinesh Beedi*'.

Robert, L Mathis and John H Jackson, *Human Resource Management*, South Western Cengage Learning, USA, 2010.

B. Dissertations and Project Reports

Mohanam, P., "Prospects and Problems of Beedi Marketing: a case study of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Cooperative Central Society Cannanore", M.Phil. Dissertation, Calicut University, 1987.

Rashmid, P.V, "Employees Absenteeism of Kerala Dinesh Food Products", Project Report, Kannur University, 2009.

Raveendran P.V, "A Study on the Art of the Financial Management in Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Cooperative Society Ltd. Kannur", M. Phil Dissertation, Calicut University, 1990.

C. Newspaper and Other Reports

Abernathy, Frederick, John Dunlop, Janice Hammond and David Weil, “A Stitch in Time: Lean Retailing and Transformation of Manufacturing – Lesson from Apparel and Textile Industries”, *Book Review*.

Annual report of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society.

Bye law of the co-operative society.

Franke, Richard W, Pyaralal Raghavan and T M Thomas Issac, “Democracy at work in Indian Industrial Co-operatives: The story of Kerala Dinesh Beedi”, *Cornell International Industrial and Labour Relation report*, 1998.

Gulati, Mitu G, Thomas Issac T M and William A Klein, *When a Worker Co-operative Works: The case of Kerala Dinesh Beedi*.

Websites

www.IndiaTradeZone.com

www.keraladinesh.com